

Studies in the cyclo-octane series:
Part VI. Condensation of Cyclo-octane-1-one-2-acetic Acid with
Primary Aromatic Amines and the Formation of
Substituted Pyrrol-2-ones

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Ethyl 2-carbethoxy cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetate, prepared by condensing ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate with ethyl bromoacetate, on hydrolysis gave cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid. This acid on refluxing with seven different primary aromatic amines furnished substituted pyrrol-2-ones.

γ -keto esters and γ -keto acids both have been found to react with arylamines at high temperatures to yield heterocyclic compounds¹; thus laevulinic acid and β -benzoyl-propionic acid when condensed with primary arylamines gave products to which structure (I) was assigned. Cyclopentan-1-one-2-acetic acid on similar condensation yielded a product for which structure (II) was proposed.

a ; R-CH₃; R₁=H

b ; R-C₆H₅; R₁=H

Mayer², had reported the isolation of two products of condensation of aniline with cyclopentan-1-one-2-acetic acid; one of these was considered to have the structure (II) while the other product was regarded as III.

Later Bertho and Kurzman³ investigated the condensation of cyclohexan-1-one-2-acetic acid with primary arylamines at high temperature and obtained 1-aryl-2-oxo-2:3:4:5:6:7-hexahydroindoles of the type IV. These cyclic products were later

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1. A. Bertho, *Agnew. Chem.*, 1955, **67**, 515; *Ber.*, 1957, **90**, 29.

2. R. Mayer., *Neure Methoden Der Preparativen Organischen Chemie*. Band II. Verlag Chemie, p. 68.

3. A. Bertho, and H. Kurzman, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, **90**, 2319.

hydrogenated in presence of Adams catalyst to give the corresponding 1-aryl-2-oxo-octahydroindoles of the type V.

(IV : Ar = C₆H₅; *o*-CH₃.C₆H₄, *m*-CH₃.C₆H₄ and *p*-CH₃.C₆H₄).

Reduction of 1-phenyl-2-oxo-octahydroindole with lithium aluminium hydride furnished 1-phenyl octahydroindole. The same product was also obtained when 1-phenyl-2-oxo-2:3:5:4:6:7-hexa-hydroindole (IV) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride.

The present communication describes the condensation of cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid with aniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *o*- and *p*-anisidines, *p*-chloroaniline and β -naphthylamine at high temperature. The above γ -keto acid was prepared by the hydrolysis of ethyl 2-carbethoxy cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetate, the latter being obtained by the condensation of ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate with ethyl bromoacetate. The heterocyclic compounds are considered to be 1-aryl-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene pyrrol-2-ones of the type VI and the presence of the carbonyl group in these products was confirmed through I.R. studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid: Ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-glyoxalate, b.p. 118-9°/11 mm., n_D^{21} 1.4768, was prepared⁴ from cyclooctanone (25 g; 0.2 mole), and ethyl oxalate (29.2 g; 0.2 mol) in presence of sodium ethoxide (sodium, 4.6 g in absolute alcohol, 100 ml). To the above ester (23 g) traces of iron powder and a small quantity of finely powdered soft glass were added and the contents distilled slowly under reduced pressure to give pure *ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate* which had b.p. 101-3°/3 mm; 113-4°/5 mm. (Yield: 20 g; 99.8%). n_D^{21} 1.4758. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 8.9. C₁₁H₁₈O₃ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.1%).

Dried sodium metal (0.34 g; 0.015 mol) was added to a solution of ethyl cyclooctan-1-one-2-carboxylate (3 g; 0.015 mol) in dry benzene and the contents refluxed until sodium dissolved. On cooling, ethyl bromoacetate (3.34 g; 0.02 mol) was added with shaking and the contents, after keeping overnight at room temperature, refluxed on a water bath until neutral (16 hrs). The cooled reaction mixture was poured into water, acidified with hydrochloric acid and the organic layer separated; the aqueous portion was extracted twice with benzene and the combined benzene extracts washed with water and dried. After removing ether, the residue on distillation gave pure *ethyl 2-carbethoxy cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetate*, b.p. 138-140°/2.6 mm. (Yield: 2.6 g; 61%). (Found: C, 63.2; H, 8.6. C₁₅H₂₄O₅ requires C, 63.4; H, 8.5%).

4. P. A. Plattner, A. Furst, and K. Jiřásek, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, **29**, 730.

The above ester (2 g) was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (50 ml; 20%) for 6 hr. on a water bath and alcohol removed. The residue was acidified with ice-cold hydrochloric acid when a colourless oil separated out; it was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried and the solvent recovered. The residue on distillation gave pure *cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid*, b.p. 161-3°/1.5 mm; it later solidified and had m.p. 71°. (Yield: 1.2 g.; 92%). (Found C, 65.0; H, 8.5. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7%).

Its *3-benzylisothiuronium salt* crystallised from hot water in colourless needles had m.p. 151° and *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* on crystallisation from dilute ethanol in red needles had m.p. 136-7°.

1-Phenyl-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene-pyrrol-2-one: A mixture of aniline (3.7 g.; 0.04 mol) and *cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid* (1.1 g; 0.006 mol) contained in a boiling tube was refluxed in an oil bath at 185-190° for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured into hydrochloric acid (10%) when an oily product separated out. This was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed free of the base, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and ether recovered. The residue on distillation gave pure *1-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene pyrrol-2-one*, b.p. 182-4°/2 mm. (Yield: 0.7 g; 29.2%). (Found: C, 79.5; H, 8.1. $C_{16}H_{19}$ ON requires C, 79.6; H, 7.9%).

1-(2'-Methyl) phenyl-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene-pyrrol-2-one was prepared by refluxing a mixture of *o*-toluidine (4.28 g; 0.04 mol) and *cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid* (1.1 g; 0.006 mol) for 8 hr and working up the reaction mixture in the manner described above; the pure product had b.p. 186°/1 mm. (Yield: 0.7 g; 27.4%). (Found: C, 79.7; H, 8.3. $C_{17}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 79.9; H, 8.3%).

1-(3'-Methyl) phenyl-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene-pyrrol-2-one prepared from *m*-toluidine (4.28 g; 0.04 mol) and *cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid* (1.1 g; 0.006 mol) in the above manner, had b.p. 199-200°/3 mm. (Yield: 0.85 g; 33.3%). (Found: C, 79.6; H, 8.3. $C_{17}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 79.9; H, 8.3%).

1-(2'-Methoxy) phenyl-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene-pyrrol-2-one, b.p. 208-9°/3 mm. was obtained by refluxing a mixture of *o*-anisidine (6 g; 0.04 mol) and *cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid* (1.1 g; 0.006 mol) at 220-230° for 8 hr and working up in the manner described above. (Yield: 0.6 g; 22.2%). (Found: C, 75.3; H, 7.9. $C_{17}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 75.2; H, 7.8%).

1-(4'-Chloro) phenyl-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene-pyrrol-2-one was obtained by refluxing a mixture of *p*-chloroaniline (5.0 g; 0.04 mol) and *cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid* (1.1 g; 0.006 mol) at 215-225° for 8 hr. and working up the reaction mixture in the customary manner, the crude product melted at 53.9°. The pure compound was obtained colourless in needles on crystallisation from methanol-petrol mixture and had m.p. 64°. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 6.5. $C_{16}H_{18}ONCl$ requires C, 69.6; H, 6.5%).

1-(2'-Naphthyl)-2:3-dihydro-4:5-hexamethylene-pyrrol-2-one: A mixture of β -naphthylamine (5.7 g; 0.04 mol) and *cyclooctan-1-one-2-acetic acid* (1.1 g; 0.006 mol) in diphenyl ether (40 ml) was gently refluxed for 8 hr. At the end of the reaction diphenyl

ether was removed under vacuum and the residue taken up in ether; the ethereal solution was worked up in the customary manner and the pure compound had b.p. 232-4°/2 mm. (Yield: 0.3 g; 19%). (Found: C, 82.0; H, 7.4. $C_{20}H_{27}ON$ requires C, 82.4; H, 7.3%).

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